

APPLICATION OF MODERN SCADA SYSTEMS IN AUTOMATION OF PROCESSES

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Annotation: In process engineering, SCADA refers to human-machine interface (HMI) systems. Today, all the leading manufacturers of process automation equipment offer one or another SCADA system. Most of them are based on personal computers running Windows 10 operating systems and provide wide functionality for building management systems for various purposes. In this process as well, the most suitable concept was selected for the development of the control system using the STEP 7 SIMATIC program. A logical model was implemented, its working graphs of selected control algorithms were created. A scheme of the control system based on the structure-information model of object behavior has been developed.

Key words: PLC, SCADA, Simatic WinCC, Microcontroller, interface, Archiving, modern, operator.

Introduction.

In the absence of visual monitoring and control in the warehouse of programmable logic controllers (PLC), it is impossible to imagine innovative systems of self-management of scientific and technical activities. Recently, in enterprises with a complex management architecture, visual control of the scientific and technical process was carried out using mnemonic diagrams and control panels with a large number of switching and signaling equipment. Currently, this equipment is replaced by new generation visualization systems called SCADA systems (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition - centralized management and data collection).

The advantage of modern visualization systems is that they not only reflect the static state of the object, but also allow:

- dynamic observation of the technological process;
- archiving of process variables with subsequent printing in the form of a report;
- controlling the process through the PC screen or operator panel using a mouse and keyboard;
- print reports and assignment forms;
- change process parameters through a computer or operator panel;

- making changes to production orders;
- saving production modes and recipes in the memory of a personal computer;
- issuing messages on the indicated events;
- control of incorrect actions of the operator, excluding subjective factors that lead to the release of low-quality products or emergency situations;
- automatically generate and print reports instead of manually filling out forms and operating logs, excluding operator errors and additions.

All SCADA systems have approximately the same configuration. Let's take a look at the architecture of the Siemens SCADA system (Fig. 1). Simatic WinCC, like many others, consists of:

- a personal computer with a visualization software package - Simatic WinCC;
- Programmable logic controller from Siemens or controller from any other manufacturer.

Communication between the computer and the PLC can be done through MPI, PROFIBUS-DP, Industrial Ethernet protocol.

Figure 1 – SCADA system construction architecture

The WinCC visualization software package allows you to control the technological process with several controllers.

The advantages and advantages of SCADA systems over outdated mnemonic diagrams are that their use not only saves space in operator rooms, but also makes production management much easier.

When using a decentralized process control architecture, the costs are:

- switching equipment;
- signaling and control fittings;
- cable products.

The use of SCADA systems is equally useful in small and large automation facilities. Rolling mills, blast furnace production, thermal power plants, pumping stations, dosing and packaging lines, warehouses, poultry farms, processing plants,

cargo flow management - this is the full range of possible applications of these systems. not a list.

Visualization systems of various manufacturers are used in the world market: Siemens, AllenBradley, GE Fanuc, Mitsubishi, ABB, Omron and others. The undisputed leader of SCADA systems in the world market is Siemens with WinCCFlexible and WinCC software packages.

SCADA - WinCC Flexible system is a modern visualization tool that meets all requirements for systems of this level. It runs under Windows 10 and consists of a Runtime program and a configuration package required for project development. WinCCFlexible allows you to program operator panels and has a faster response time than traditional SCADA systems. It is used to view plants and small productions in any industry as a single system and can also be connected to a higher-level system (for example, WinCC).

The open SCADA system allows easy and simple integration of the Simatic WinCC operator interface into newly created or existing automation projects. This powerful software product from Siemens avoids the high costs of software design and debugging. It is important that WinCC supports the Russian language. This system has everything you need for advanced imaging systems.

Microcontroller selection criteria.

It includes the use of the SCADA system for monitoring the control facility, compressor station, technological facilities, data collection and control. The architecture of the industrial control system is centralized - this system architecture includes one microprocessor controller for several technological objects.

The SCADA system includes the following components:

- operator's workplace;
- microprocessor controller level;
- level of field devices.

The interaction of the dispatch center and technological equipment in the monitoring and control system is carried out by the microprocessor controller, which is the basis of any dispatch monitoring and control system. The data received from the sensors enters the controller, where it is processed and based on the results of the processing, a control action is generated. The processed data is sent to the control panel, where the entire process of control and regulation is monitored, and if necessary, the operator intervenes in the technological process of oil heating.

The microprocessor controller used in the system must provide the following functions:

- input/output, analog-to-digital conversion, averaging, scaling, noise filtering, reliability testing;
- data exchange with the workstation;

- automatic management and regulation;
- execution of remote commands from the workstation.

Analog input modules must support input signals from thermal resistance and input current signals (4÷20 mA) combined with full galvanic isolation of digital and analog parts.

Discrete modules must provide complete galvanic isolation of internal circuits from external circuits. Discrete input modules must provide 12÷24 V signals and a current of no more than 5 mA/signal. Discrete output modules must provide a current of up to 5 A at voltages up to ~ 220 V.

Data exchange between the controller and the computer must be done via the RS-232 or RS-485 serial port.

Controllers of such families: SLC 500, Direct Logic, MOSCAD, Siemens, etc. has an incomparably higher price due to the higher price (modern and more expensive chips, transportation costs, customs fees). At the same time, they are superior to controllers of other brands in a number of indicators, for example:

- reliability;
- work;
- ease of programming, etc.

STEP 7 SIMATIC programming

STEP 7 is a standard software package used to configure and program SIMATIC programmable logic controllers. It is part of the SIMATIC industrial program.

The first step in software development is hardware configuration. The configuration is carried out using the Hardware Configuration tool (Fig. 2), in which the software configuration of the hardware of the automation system is carried out.

Slot	Module	Order number	Firmware	MPI address	I address	Q address
1	PS 307 2A	6ES7 307-1BA00-0AA0				
2	CPU 313	6ES7 313-1AD03-0AB0	V1.1	3		
3						
4	AI8x14Bit	6ES7 331-7HF01-0AB0			256...271	
5	DI16xDC48-125V	6ES7 321-1CH80-0AA0			4...5	
6	DO16xDC24V/0.5A	6ES7 322-1BH10-0AA0				8...9
7	DO16xDC24V/0.5A	6ES7 322-1BH10-0AA0				12...13
8						
9						
10						
11						

Figure 2 – Hardware setup

The second stage is the description of input and output variables, as well as variables used directly in program blocks (small programs). Variables are described in the "Symbols" tool (Figure 3).

	Status	Symbol	Address	Data type	Comn
1		T1	T 1	TIMER	
2		stop	I 4.1	BOOL	
3		Scale	FC 105	FC 105	
4		P1	Q 8.3	BOOL	
5		OG	Q 8.7	BOOL	
6		N	Q 8.6	BOOL	
7		Komp	Q 8.5	BOOL	
8		K1	Q 8.2	BOOL	
9		D6_tempposlepeci	MD 124	REAL	
10		D6_r	MD 120	REAL	
11		D6_i	PIW 776	INT	
12		D5_tempdopeci	MD 116	REAL	
13		D5_r	MD 112	REAL	
14		D5_i	PIW 772	INT	
15		D4_rashod	MD 84	REAL	
16		D4_r	MD 80	REAL	
17		D4_i	PIW 760	INT	
18		D3_temperatura	MD 94	REAL	
19		D3_r	MD 90	REAL	
20		D3_i	PIW 764	INT	
21		D2_r	MD 104	REAL	
22		D2_i	PIW 768	INT	
23		D2_davlenie	MD 108	REAL	
24		D1	I 4.0	BOOL	
25		B1	Q 8.4	BOOL	
26					

Figure 3 – Table of variables

The next step was to implement the analog signal recording function (Figure 4).

Contents Of: 'Environment\Interf

Interface

FC3 : Title:

Comment:

Network 1: Title:

Comment:

```

CALL FC 106
IN      :=#XF1           #XF1
HI_LIM :=#H_ON_1        #H_ON_1
LO_LIM :=#L_ON_1        #L_ON_1
BIPOLAR:=#POL_ON        #POL_ON
RET_VAL:=LW16
OUT     :=#VIHOD        #VIHOD
    
```

Figure 4 - Analog signal recording function

Data exchange between the lower level (Step7) and the higher level (WinCC flexible) is carried out via the MPI protocol. For this purpose, the variables are described in the built-in database (Tag List) (Figure 5).

Name	Connection	Data type	Symbol	Address	Array elements	Acquisition cycle	Comment
A_Tp_ustavka	Connection_1	Real	A_Tp_ustavka	MD 60	1	1 s	
D_Tp	Connection_1	Real	D_Tp	MD 14	1	1 s	
D_Tvh	Connection_1	Real	D_Tvh	MD 120	1	1 s	
D_Tvyh	Connection_1	Real	D_Tvyh	MD 16	1	1 s	
D_Tvyh_zad	Connection_1	Real	D_Tvyh_zad	MD 74	1	1 s	
R_Lampa_niz	Connection_1	Bool	R_Lampa_niz	Q 8.0	1	1 s	предупреждение нижней предел
R_Lampa_verh	Connection_1	Bool	R_Lampa_verh	Q 8.1	1	1 s	предупреждение верхней предел
R_oshinka	Connection_1	Real	R_oshinka	MD 54	1	1 s	
R_vyh_reg	Connection_1	Real	R_vyh_reg	MD 56	1	1 s	

Figure 5 - SCADA interface - compressor station system development.

Package structure

The interface design was carried out using WinCC Flexible, a high-level system designed for the development of visualization systems.

Windows Control Center (WinCC) Flexible is an environment for the development and implementation of high-level automated process control programs. This is a SCADA system (control and data acquisition system).

WinCC Flexible is used to visualize the technological process and develop a graphical operator interface.

WinCC Flexible enables the operator to monitor the movement. The process is displayed graphically on the screen. In this case, the reflection is updated when the state of the process changes.

WinCC is a modular system. The main components are Configuration Software (CS) and Runtime Software (RT).

WinCC Explorer opens immediately after starting WinCC. WinCC Explorer is the core of the engineering system. WinCC Explorer shows the structure of the entire project. In addition, project management is carried out here.

Special editors for configuration can be called from WinCC Explorer. Each editor is used to create a specific WinCC subsystem.

Figure 6 – WinCC navigation window

The most important WinCC subsystems:

- graphic system; The graphics editor used to create the process images is called the Graphics Designer;
- alarm message registration system; The message configuration process is performed by the Alarm Logging editor;
- archiving system; A tag log editor is used to identify data to be archived;
- reporting system; The editor for creating report templates is called the Report Designer.
- a user management system whose editor is called User Administrator.
- The communication system is configured directly in WinCC Explorer.

All configuration information is stored in the CS database.

Texnologik jarayonda WinCC flexible-da Grafik Dizayn.

Graphic Design in WinCC flexible in the technological process.

Runtime software allows the user to monitor and control the process. The execution system is mainly used to solve the following problems:

- reading data stored in the CS database;
- display process frames on the screen;
- interaction with the automation system;
- archiving of current process data, such as process values and event messages;
- process control, for example, inputting, enabling/disabling operator-defined values.

WinCC is an open system. It can use various ActiveX components, dynamically loaded program libraries (DLL), implement OLE (object linking and embedding) objects, and use data exchange through DDE (dynamic data exchange).

A "graphic editor" was used to study mnemonic diagrams. Graphical editor is a tool for visualization of controlled scientific and technical properties and timely delivery control, supports ActiveX and OLE technologies. Graphic Designer

combines tools for learning and viewing graphical mnemonic diagrams of automated workstations for dispatchers. The mnemonic diagram of the compressor station is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - use of the SCADA system in the technological process.

Conclusions.

Based on the technological processes, it can be said that the introduction of the control system will reduce the consumption of energy resources due to the rational operation mode of the compressor unit, increase the productivity of equipment and timely management of scientific and technical activities, as well as reduce the level of accidents and extend the service life of the equipment. increase, reduce the impact of the human factor on the production process and immediately increase the culture of production.

The creation of the system allows it to be produced without limitations in accordance with integration with other existing or newly created systems and, if necessary, without significant costs, to increase the number of performed functions and signal processing channels.

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